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Mental Health in Digital Age

Abstract

Mental health encompasses emotional, social and psychological well-being. It influences the individual at affective, cognitive and behavioural levels. Mental health per se is deciphered when a person makes choices, copes with a distressed event or situation and when relating to others. With the advent of digital technology, primarily, computer, laptop, mobile telephony, etc., there are noticeable changes with regard to attitudes and behaviour, particularly, maladaptive ones, like changes in mood patterns and social behaviour. Nevertheless, technology has become the part of one's daily lives and helps in engaging a person in online facilities of online shopping, banking, maintaining a relationship with significant others, maintaining a professional profile and exploring how we are and what we show to others. Digital technology has a strong interface each one influencing the other. On a similar note, technology offers application for mobile and web-based services for enhancing one's mental health. Technology has the capacity to influence human beings and also has the capability to offer preventive measures for poor mental health.

Key words: *Mental health, digital technology, affective, cognitive and behavioural*

Introduction

Engagement in cyberspace (space within which communication occurs via the internet) is a necessary activity in the era of digitization. Keeping in view the all pervasiveness of digitization of information, the concerns arising are whether mental health is being enhanced or diminished in the present times, what are the challenges emerging thereby and the benefits in the digital world. These are a few questions that will be addressed in the present article.

Health per se includes both physical health and mental health. But most often, any discourse on health generally focuses on just the physical aspects.

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Brock Chisholm, the first Director-General of the World Health Organization (WHO), in 1954, stated that, “Without mental health, there can be no true physical health.” Mental health, as defined by WHO, “is a state of well-being in which an individual can realize his or her own potential, cope with the normal stresses of life, work productively, and make a contribution to the community.” Ryff and Singer (1998) opine that health is a complete state, consisting of not just the absence of illness but also the presence of something positive. The markers of mental health include perceived life satisfaction, generally positive emotions, optimism, purpose in life, healthy relationships with others, and self-acceptance. Mental health thus, is regarded as an optimal psychological state that becomes a necessary goal to be obtained by the populace in all the societies. Nevertheless, it is greatly influenced by biological, psychological and environmental factors.

Given the fact that mental health contributes significantly in overall development, two important goals related to mental health defined by WHO under Sustainable Development Goals (September 2015) were considered. The first is to reduce by one-third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases (behavioural, developmental, and neurological disorders) through prevention and treatment and to promote mental health and well-being by 2030. Secondly, to strengthen the prevention and treatment of substance use disorder(s), including narcotic drug use and harmful use of alcohol. It may be highlighted here that mental health is a major public health concern in both developing and developed societies. For example, anxiety and depression are the most common disorders in developed countries like the US and the UK, just to name a few. About 20-25% people in UK, and US experience mental illness in a given year. Mental health problems not only impact them economically, but its ramifications are observed in all aspects of life, like children dropping out of school, behavioural problems, delinquent behaviour, inattentiveness, distress, anxiety disorders and the like.

Status of Mental Illness in India

A recent survey on the state of mental illness in India, National Mental Health Survey (2016) was conducted by National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences (NIMHANS), Bangalore in 12 states of the country. It is estimated that approximately 150 million people in India are experiencing one or the other kind of mental health problems. As per the survey, 13.7% experience various disorders. Prevalence of mental disorders including common mental health disorders, severe mental health disorders, and alcohol and substance use disorders (excluding tobacco use disorder) in adults over the age of 18 years, is

about 10.6% and most of whom require immediate interventions show 1.9% suffering from severe mental disorders.

The major findings that emerged are:

- the prevalence of mental illness is high in urban metropolitan areas,
- neurosis and stress related disorders are twice as high in women as compared to males, and nearly 50% of people with major depressive disorders face difficulty in carrying out their daily activities.
- The common psychological problems reported by participants (total participants were 34802, above the age of 18 years) are:
 - problems in anger management,
 - emotional instability,
 - lack of tolerance, and
 - reduced attention span.

The survey points that poverty and inaccessibility to basic amenities that are essential to mental health and well being are missing. The report also states that due to stigmatization of mental illness, there are huge gaps in the treatment modalities and the patient is often left untreated in most cases, even after 12 months of illness. Since mental health is not a priority, like physical health, there is a paucity of mental health specialists as well. Among the 12 states covered in the survey, Manipur had the highest prevalence of mental disorders.

Another multi-site survey (2017) conducted by Department of Psychiatry, AIIMS, Delhi, in 11 cities across India (total participants were 24371 above 18 years) concluded that women had a higher prevalence of anxiety and mood disorders. The most important finding was the huge treatment gap of about 95% - only 5 of 100 individuals with common mental disorders received any treatment over the past year. (The study focused on twelve-month prevalence and treatment gap for common mental disorders) Women were twice more likely than men to have anxiety disorders (4.42% women, 2.44% men), and 1.16 times (1.79% women, 1.11% men) more likely to have mood disorders. Substance use on the other hand was more common among men (2.23% men, 0.08% women).

Digital Technologies: Harmful or Empowering

The cyber world has immense information. It has been regarded as informative, convenient, and resourceful with economic and social benefits. The cyberspace is being used and misused at the same time. And, in this context, it is a double-edged sword. With reference to misuse of technology, Internet Addiction (IA) has recently been added in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual*

of Mental Disorders (DSM–5). In defence of IA being included in the manual, Block (2008) states “Internet addiction is a compulsive-impulsive spectrum disorder that involves online/ and or offline computer usage and consists of at least three subtypes, excessive gaming, sexual preoccupations and email/text messaging”. Block further suggests that IA shows commonality with substance use disorders, like excessive use, withdrawal phenomenon, tolerance and negative influences. Presently, IA is a major public health concern in China and South Korea.

Interface of Individual and Digital Technology

Digital technology has become all pervasive in our everyday and work lives, and its importance will continue to increase in future. The innovations in digital technology have not only brought in various threats, but also opportunities. For example, it acts as a facilitator in delivery of health services to the society. Access to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been a key driver of development. The number of internet users in India is expected to reach 500 Million by June, 2018 (Internet and Mobile Association of India). There has been an increase of 11.30% from December 2016 to December 2017. The internet penetration in urban India is 64.84% while as, rural internet penetration is 20.26% (December, 2017).

In light of the above data, it is assured that more and more people will be able to access cyberspace in future. The new technologies like video conferencing, smart mobile devices, virtual world, and electronic games, etc. are here to stay. These new technologies alter the human experience as well as health care. It is also a challenge to psychologists of how it is changing the ways of communication and processing information. The community of netizens that includes ‘digital natives and digital immigrants’ (Pransky, 2001), and the advances in technology is increasing at an exponential rate. Digital natives are the generation of young people who are ‘native speakers’ of the digital language of computers, games and internet. While the digital immigrants have not been exposed to digital technology at an early age, exponential growth in technology has enabled, facilitated and augmented new services for mental health care where self-monitoring is possible and autonomy in decision making is present. This may happen with or without professional involvement also.

Digital technology, being a part of modern day living, helps individuals to interact in cyberspace and how these interactions affect lives outside the realm of cyberspace also becomes significant. It has been rightly pointed out, that digital technology has the capacity to enhance or diminish mental health. There are potential risks involved in cyberspace as its negative outcomes, like being

exposed to danger, harm and hazards. In other words, it may have favourable and not favourable consequences. It has been observed that people develop a habitual pattern of overuse of technology with increase in screen time (mobile, laptop, computer and television) to the extent of impairing healthy functioning.

Usage of Cyberspace According to Developmental Stages

The usage of digital technologies differs across developmental stages. Though, variations do exist within the group also, but overall the pattern observed (Third, et al. 2014) is as follows:

1. Children: The primary need for children (upto the age of 11 years) to use digital technology, primarily, is for entertainment, watching cartoons via streaming videos or playing online games. The UNICEF report on 'State of the World's Children: Children in Digital World', states that 1 out of 3 internet users, worldwide is a child. Parents also use technology to pacify infants and children. Researcher Jenny Radesky at Boston University School of Medicine points out that this strategy used by parents may have negative consequences for social and emotional development. Children face difficulty in developing emotional self-regulation and social competence. Children are able to register themselves on adult social networking sites where their age cannot be verified. Children also become target to free online games like, 'advergaming' intended to interest children for their products. Most often the advertisement is for unhealthy foods for which the children might be greatly influenced. (Independent, 29 March 2014) Children also are exposed to cyber-bullying, and may be contacted and connected digitally with strangers. This age group is also vulnerable to getting access to pornographic and/or violent content unintentionally. The online and offline risks for this age group are more or less same. In order to overcome the risks, parents should be familiar with the technology and vigilant about their children's online activities. The problems encountered thereof, are likely to be in developing social competence and emotional regulation. According to American Paediatrics' Association, digital media exposure of children of all ages should be limited to the bare minimal.

2. Adolescents: For this age group, of 12 to 17 years, technology is primarily used to socialize with peers, both, for communication as well as for entertainment. The risks involved, in this age group includes, cyber-bullying, 'sexting', violation of privacy, being exposed to sexual images and text. Many a times, adolescents are also not aware of the legal implications of some online activities like, 'sexting'. Development of aggressive behaviours like self-harm, truancy, neglecting school duties, addictive behaviours are all common problems in this stage of developments.

3. Adults: For the age group from 18-64 years, cyberspace is primarily used for gathering information, shopping, banking and communication. The Pew Research Centre (2014) reported that 73% of adults have witnessed online harassment, such as being threatened, cyber-stalking, and sexual harassment. Adults are also at risk of online fraud, embezzling of funds and identities thefts.

4. Seniors: Adults above 65 years, primarily use cyberspace to maintain contact with friends and family, receive or send updates of significant others who are not in close proximity, for medical purpose, and information for local services. At times, seniors may also use cyberspace for online gaming. Seniors are not particularly aware of misuse of cyberspace and thus, can be particularly vulnerable to cyber criminals.

Thus, it may be said that people who use technology more often are at a greater risk, but both children and seniors are almost equally vulnerable in cyberspace. The other risks involved in cyberspace are content-related risks, conduct-related risks, contact-related risks, and other risks. (Livingstone, Kirwil, Ponte and Staksrud, 2013) Researchers have concluded that the risks involved with content are primarily because of pornographic or violent content. This type of content many a times pops up accidentally and thus, is more shocking and upsetting. Violent content may be frightening and cause anxiety disorders. Contact-related risks include people assuming false personalities, impersonating someone and later, even trying to meet face-to-face. Conduct-related risks include hacking of information, sharing images without consent, and cyber-bullying. Cyber-bullying has been linked to many negative mental health problems like, depression, social anxiety, somatic symptoms, poor self-esteem, increased school absences and lowered academic performance. Researchers have found an association between victimization in cyberspace and suicidal behavior. At workplace, cyber-bullying may cause high levels of stress that may lead to severe anxiety related disorders, and depression, decrease in productivity, lack of job satisfaction and increased absenteeism.

Cyberspace for Delivering Mental Health Services

Delivering mental health services very quickly is one the biggest advantage of digital technology. As mental health refers to positive functioning, promoting mental health and treating mental illness should go hand in hand. Delivery of mental health services in developing countries is at a very slow pace. For example, India was facing a possible “mental health epidemic” and not simply a challenge. Addressing the concern, President Kovind in his address in NIMHANS, 2017, stressed the need for providing access to treatment facilities to all those suffering from mental disorders, by the year, 2022.

To achieve this objective, and to bridge the burgeoning gap between service providers and the unmet needs of the patients, there has to be an increased use of ICT to improve the health care mechanism and access to services. Digital movement in mental health care or e-mental health is a cultural phenomenon that has empowered patients to exercise greater choice and control. The online space helps in overcoming stigma, helps in prevention and in practical interventions in community settings. The services for e-health and m-health already exist. Similarly, now we have e-mental health on the same lines that uses ICT to support and improve mental health with the use of online resources, social media, and smart-phone application. Given the fact, that there are only 43 government-run hospitals across India to provide services to more than seventy million people living with mental disorders and 0.30 psychiatrists, 0.17 nurses, and .05 psychologists per 1 Lakh mentally ill patients in the country being available, the role of ICT becomes really significant.

There are two types of e-mental health that one commonly refers to, one being web interventions and the second is mobile applications (MHapps), referred to as Internet- and mobile –based psychological interventions (IMIs). Another delivery mechanism related to it is tele-mental health, a subset of tele-health that uses video-conferencing techniques to provide mental health services from a distance. It includes, tele-psychology, tele-psychiatry, tele-mental nursing and tele-behavioural health. An example of tele-psychiatry is SCARF's (Schizophrenia Research Foundation, based in Chennai) use of mobile clinics in rural India. This has been used since 2005, when it started counselling Tsunami victims through video conferencing. It has also introduced mobile tele-psychiatry since 2010. Blogging and social media have also shown their positive impact.

The basic premise of using digital technology in providing mental health services is to ensure that everyone has access to mental health and emotional health support is available at all times. This also serves the purpose of reaching the under-served sections of the population in society, at all times using synchronous or asynchronous text communication for screening, prevention, therapy and measure his/her mood, behavior, psycho-education and so on.

Mental health services have so far followed a traditional path of face-to-face therapy in clinical settings and, more often than not, away from the normal lives that the patients lead. But now with hordes of mobile applications that are available on the net, the patient can record, activities in real-time and share information with the therapist. Early detection of problems, greater engagement in one's care, timely adjustment of the problem, and shared decision making, flexibility, are a few of the benefits of these innovations. Secondly, this modality has paved the way for more objectivity, and reliability to the process of

assessment, diagnosis, and monitoring. This has been validated by few studies as well. Thirdly, it addresses the concern of the under-served. It also helps in overcoming social stigma, and social isolation. There is an increase in social media platforms, thereby impacting the ability to access information and support from peers and professionals in informal ways. At present, a large section of young adults are afflicted with mental health issues and this is the largest group using ICT also. Such a platform can enable the provision of such services to those who will not otherwise, go for traditional ways of treatment, and thereby maintain some semblance of anonymity. Lastly, it will also sensitize general masses about mental health and will be able to address the low psychologist to patient ratio challenge in India, in a cost-effective manner. Blended mode, i.e., combining face-to-face traditional approach with the Internet-and mobile-based approach also has the potential of increasing the effect of psychological intervention as well as being cost-effective at the same time.

Challenges

Digital technology has a huge potential in delivering and transforming mental health services in a developing country like, India. However, there are a few gaps to realize this potential. Primarily, the ‘digital divide’, or the gap between people who do not have access to technology and those who have access to technology is one of the biggest challenges. Also people who face certain barriers in using the technology like the elderly and the senior citizens, intellectually disabled, and people who are not able to adapt the technology, may also not benefit from the services. Hence, customizing the device to the needs of such a group is particularly important.

Secondly, there is an absence of any clear cut guidelines with regard to mental health services being provided in the cyberspace. Specific guidelines for licensure, referrals, privacy, screening, assessment, record-keeping, etc., are the present day requirement. The American Psychological Association guidelines for the practice of tele-psychology, in general are being applied and that includes standards on informed consent, competence to practice, confidentiality, doing no harm, and on how termination, interruption of services, payments, technology disposal and inter jurisdictional practices. Apart from this, training is required for the software being used when treatment is being planned.

Lastly, trial-based experimental validation and randomized trial of the mental health applications is also required. This would help in public acceptability of innovative methods for delivering mental health services.

Conclusion

In light of the above discussion, it may be said that mental health and mental

illness can be addressed positively within the cyberspace and paradoxically, cyberspace also has the potential of mental health risks and threats for its users. Bullying, harassment, sexual activities and sexual predators and pedophiles, gaming and gambling, deception, scams, frauds and pornography are all happening in the cyberspace. Technological innovations in ICT are thrusting new challenges for the psychologists. In light of these facts, technology can and should be used in a healthy way for progress. Apart from conventional media, the online space is also another way forward in creating awareness, access to treatment and adoption of preventive measures about mental health. ICT has the potential to cater to underserved population and to address mental health issues. Face-to-face consultations has so far not been able to meet the needs of large number of people and so cyber solutions in mental health services in the country promises a healthy functioning life.

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